

Health risk tendencies of some municipal solid waste dumps in Otukpo, Benue State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Solid dumpsites within Otukpo, Benue State, Nigeria were randomly selected. The constituents of the dumps were studied, identified and classified into harmful and nonharmful ones. The bacterial flora was also studied to determine the potential of the dumps to health hazards. The result indicated that plants wastes were generated more, having the highest quantity (14.42%) of the total components collected. Food residue amounted to about 13.10%, while glasses, newspapers and woods had < 9%. Human faecal constituents had the least percentage of 4.90%. The biodegradable bulk occupied an average 68.29% while the nonbiodegradable constituents were about 31.71%. Organisms isolated per cross zone tabulation indicated that Zone B had the highest number of organisms (160/ml) and the least (50/ml) was found in Zone A. Prevalence revealed that *E. coli* was the highest followed by *Streptococcus faecalis* (30.43%), *Klebsiella* sp. (16.98%) *Staphylococcus aureus* (16%) and *Salmonella* sp. constituted the least (13.04%). The dumps are mostly domestic dumps and the bacteria isolated were found to be pathogenic but their presence and possibility to accumulate pose as a serious threat to the populace. These dumpsites also serve as breeding grounds for the vectors/carriers of the other non-bacterial pathogens; these collectively pose a great threat to the inhabitants of the study area. A survey from the hospitals around zones sampled also revealed the prevalence of malaria, typhoid, dysentery, tetanus, diarrhoea, bronchitis, ascariasis, asthma, eye infections, filariasis, cholera and pneumonia. This suggested that the dumps could probably be the sources of pathogens that are responsible for these infections.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Thousands of tonnes of solid wastes are generated daily in Africa [2]. Most of the wastes end up in open dumps and wetlands, contaminating surface and ground water and posing major health hazards. According to Asomani-Boateng, *et al.* [4], generation rates, available only for select cities and regions, are approximately 0.5 kilograms per person per day; in some cases reaching as high as 0.8 kilograms per person per day. While this may seem modest compared to the 1–2 kg per person per day generated in developed countries, most wastes in Africa is not collected by municipal collection systems because of poor management, fiscal irresponsibility or

malfeasance, equipment failure, or inadequate waste management budgets as reported by Egberé *et al.* [8]. Adedibu [1] attested to the fact that the quantity and generation rate of solid wastes in Nigeria have increased at an alarming rate over the years with lack of efficient and modern technology for the management of the wastes.

Throughout most of sub-Saharan Africa solid waste generation exceeds collection capacity. This is in part due to rapid urban population growth; while only 35 percent of the sub-Saharan population lives in urban areas, the urban population grew by 150 percent between 1970 and 1990. A publication by the Federal Ministry of Housing and Environment [14],

indicated that solid waste from some Nigeria cities are biodegradable from food processing and other ruminants with figures varying between low and high density areas. Sometimes the degree of contamination is such that such resources cannot be restored to previous state of pure quality at which point such air, water or soil constitutes a very serious health hazard [15].

Ogunjobi [13], stated that all the states of Nigeria may be highly polluted, largely from domestic solid wastes, with as many as 25% of the people living in these towns of population ranging from 20,000 to more than 4 million. Problems posed by the wastes include eye sore they create, purifying organic matter producing nauseating odours. The dumps also constitute breeding ground for disease causing microorganisms, rodents and flies.

Solid waste is the unwanted or useless solid materials generated from combined residential, industrial and commercial activities in a given area. It may be categorized according to its origin (domestic, industrial, commercial, construction or institutional); according to its

contents (organic material, glass, metal, plastic paper etc); or according to hazard potential (toxic, non-toxin, flammable, radioactive, infectious etc) [11]. Similarly, Adeyeba and Okpala [3] stated that rotting organic materials pose great public health risks, including, as mentioned above, serving as breeding grounds for disease vectors. Waste handlers and waste pickers are especially vulnerable and may also become carriers, contracting and transmitting diseases when human or animal excreta or medical wastes are in the wastes stream [8].

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Study area description

Otukpo Local Government Area (LGA) is one of the oldest Local Government Areas in Benue State. It is located on Latitude 7° 13' 57" North and Longitude 8° 05' 26" East with a population of 261,666 and landmass of 390sq.km and has predominantly Idoma native inhabitants. The dry season is usually from November to March while the wet (rainy) season from May to October.

Figure: 1. Map of Otukpo Metropolis Showing sampling Zones

2.2 Dump site inspection

Visits were made to the various dumpsites for physical inspection. During this visits, there were interaction with some identified waste pickers found at site. The sites include; Babylon, Okokoro, Okenyi, Ijami, and Ojira dumpsites (Figure 1). During the wet (rainy) season the fermentation and decomposition of the

biodegradable are very high compare to that of dry season; these produce unpleasant odours, and constitute nuisance.

2.3 Sampling sites selection

The Zones for this study were selected at randomly.

Zone A: is situated at the Government Reservation Area (GRA). It is characterized by low-density of house that are mostly fenced, and sparsely populated by the rich. The dumpsites are few and small.

Zone B: is located at old township site popularly called Ipigelli comprises of mostly low-grade, high-density houses only few were fenced and this area is densely populated. Dumpsites here are large heaps.

Zone C: is located at Sabon-gari, characterized by high-density people. The Dumpsites are large heaps similar to that of Zone B. There are high commercial activities here.

2.4 Sample collection

The municipal solid waste were collected randomly from the five sampling sites for a period of two months (March and April) 2012, spanning over two seasons (rainy and dry season). Sample containers were thoroughly washed several times with water and later rinsed with deionized water.

2.5 Treatment of soil samples

Waste sample were collected once a week for the period of three weeks making a total of thirty (30) samples from all the dumpsites within the period of two months (March - April) 2012. At each sampling zone, the surface debris was removed and subsurface soil dug to a depth of about 5cm was scooped from one-foot square area into sterile duplicate sampling bottles and appropriately labeled. Ten samples, two from each site, were collected on each visit. The sterile gloves and facemasks were worn during collection of wastes as safety precaution. After collection, waste samples were immediately taken to the laboratory within 2 hours.

2.5.1 Preparation of soil sample

Soil samples were air-dried and sieved through 0.2mm wire mesh to obtain fine soil particles [9]. Ten gram (10g) of each air-dried fine soil sample was mixed in a test-tube containing 50ml, of sterile deionizer water using a sterile glass rod.

2.5.2 Soil extraction for use in agar plate

Seventy five grammes (75g) of the fertile soil was weighed with a weighing balance and placed in 500ml Erlenmeyer flask. Three hundred milliliters of tap water was poured into the flask and the flask was plugged with cotton wool and autoclaved at 121°C for 30minutes and allowed to cool. The supernatant was filtered with clean cloth then with filter paper. One tenth gramme of CaCO₃ was added to the filtrate and allowed for 5 minutes to precipitate the cloudiness in filtrate. The final volume of the filtrate was adjusted to 200ml with tap water [5].

2.6 Bacteriological analysis

2.6.1 Serial dilution

Each soil sample was serially diluted and 1ml each of the dilution plated on MacConkey agar, CLED or nutrient agar to obtain viable count. One ml (1ml) of water sample was transferred into 9ml of sterile deionised water in a test tube using a 1ml pipette. The mixture was thoroughly shaken to ensure proper mixing. Another transfer was made from this mixture to a second test tube containing 9ml of deionised water. This was done serially and the fourth dilution (10⁴) was considered and poured into Petri dishes. The pipette used was discarded after each sample. The plate showing colonies were counted. Morphological and Biochemical test such as Gram staining technique, catalase test, coagulate test were used for differentiation of gram positive bacteria essentially *Staphylococcus* and *Streptococcus* were carried out [7].

2.6.2 Inoculation into medium

About 0.1ml each of dilution 10³ and 10⁴ from serial dilution of the soil sample was placed in each of the two sterile dishes. To each of the petri dishes, 20.0ml of soil extract agar (previously prepared) at approximately 45°C was poured and rotated by hand in a broad swirling motion so that the inoculums was uniformly dispensed in the medium. The agar was allowed to solidify and was incubated at 37 °C for 48 hours.

2.6.3 Characterization and identification of bacterial isolates

A total of five (5) bacterial isolate were identified using conventional microbiological and biochemical procedures which include microscopic examination of cell morphology. The tests were carried out according to the methods previously [6,7].

2.6.4 Counting of colonies

A colony counter was used to count different colonies. Petri dishes with microbial growth were placed under the colony counter one after the other and they were counted accordingly [5].

2.6.5 Coagulase test

This test is used to identify *organisms that* produce the enzyme coagulase. A drop of distilled water was placed on each end of a clean slide. A sterile wire loop was used to remove a colony of gram positive organism. An emulsion of the colony was made on the slide. A lapful of plasma was added to the suspension and mixed gently and the other left as control. The suspension was allowed to stand for ten seconds and observed for clumping [7].

2.6.6 Catalase test

This test was used to differentiate those bacteria that produce the enzyme catalase such as; staphylococci from non-catalase producing bacteria such as; streptococci according to the method of [7]. 2ml of hydrogen peroxide solution was poured into a test tube; several colonies of the organism were removed by a sterile glass rod and immersed into the hydrogen peroxide solution. Active bubbling of oxygen observed confirmed *Staphylococcus* species (positive catalase test), where no bubbles appeared, confirmed *Streptococcus* sp.

2.6.7 Gram staining technique

To prepare a smear, a colony from petri dishes was picked individually by a wire loop and emulsified in a drop of sterile distilled water on the slide. The smear was air dried, and the smear was allowed to cool before staining it. The fixed smear was covered with crystal violet stain for thirty to sixty seconds (30-60 sec.) after which stain was washed off with clean tap water. The water was tipped off and the smear covered with lugol's iodine for 30-60 seconds. The iodine was washed off with clean tap water for few seconds and the smear was decolourised with acetone and washed off immediately with clean tap water. The smear was counterstained with safranin for two minutes and the stain was later washed off with clean tap water. The smear was air dried by placing the slide in a draining rack. The smear was viewed under the microscopic with the objective lens (x100) to check the morphological characteristics of the bacteria cell. The cell that were not decolourised by the safranin were identified as gram positive while those that retained the colour of safranin were identified as gram negative bacteria [6].

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Analyses of samples

From the 15 municipal solid wastes samples collected from the different dumpsites of the study area, twelve different types of wastes were identified and classified into biodegradable and non-biodegradable.

Table: 1. shows the percentage colonization of some harmful microorganisms that can be a threat to human life. It can be read that, at all the zones studied, *Escherichia coli* had the greatest percentage (52% 45.28% and 43.47% respectively) among all the organisms observed. Whilst *Klebsiella* sp was least at station A and *Staphylococcus aureus* was least at stations B and C.

Figure: 2. The weight of solid wastes (in grams) and the analysis of the results indicated that plant waste matter (leaves, grasses, and stumps) had the highest percentage weight (14.42%) followed by food residues 13.10% while human faeces sampled had the least average percentage weight of 4.90%. The result shown in Figure 2 reveals that plant waste matter had the highest average of 72%, followed by food residues (13%) and the least was the human faeces sampled.

The prevalence of organism at each site is presented in Table 2, it can be seen that Zone B owing to the nature of the dump site is the most devastating among all, where the investigated organisms are in high abundance and could cause endemic of diseases associated with these organisms. However the Hospital survey reports from this zone registered incidences that residents have suffered from illnesses related with the organisms but the route of infections have not been ascertained (Table 3). However, Table 2 shows the biochemical characteristics some of pathogenic bacteria isolated from the waste dumps, where catalase test revealed the presence of four bacteria namely: *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus* *Klebsiella* sp and *Salmonella* sp. Gram stain and Coagulase shows the presence of *Staph aureus* and *Streptococcus faecalis*.

Table 1. Organisms isolated and their percentage occurrences in zones sampled.

Zone A			Zone B			Zone C		
Organisms	No. of colonies	%	Organisms	No. of colonies	%	Organisms	No. of colonies	%
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	8	16	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	12	11.32	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	3	3.26
<i>Streptococcus faecalis</i>	12	24	<i>Streptococcus faecalis</i>	25	23.58	<i>Streptococcus faecalis</i>	28	30.43
<i>Klebsiella</i> sp	4	8	<i>Klebsiella</i> sp	18	16.98	<i>Klebsiella</i> sp	9	9.78
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	26	52	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	48	45.28	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	40	43.47
			<i>Salmonella</i> sp	3	2.83	<i>Salmonella</i> sp	12	13.04
Total	50	100		106	100		92	100

Table 2. Biochemical characteristics of isolated organisms from the dumpsites.

Organisms	Catalase test	Gram stain test	Coagulase test
<i>Streptococcus faecalis</i>	-	+	+
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	+	-	-
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	+	+	+
<i>Klebsiella</i> sp	+	-	-
<i>Salmonella</i> sp	+	-	-

Table 3. Biodegradable and nonbiodegradable municipal solid wastes sampled.

Biodegradable	Nonbiodegradable
Food residues	Glass
News paper	Metals
Plant waste matters	Polythene bags
Textile	Plastics
Human faecal sample	
Cardboard sheets	
Mattress	
Wood	

CONCLUSION

This study examined the environmental and health implications of solid waste disposal to people living in close proximity of wastes dumpsites. It can be observed that human faeces serve as a collection centre and good medium for these pathogens and dumpsite encourage the defecation by human of faeces which serve as toilets to passersby and strangers because is seen as without owners. This agrees with Gouveia and Ruscitto [12] who high-lighted that in a number of health surveys a wide range of health problems, including respiratory systems, irritation of the skin, eyes and nose, gastrointestinal problems, psychological disorders, and allergies, have been discovered. The dumpsites studied revealed that it has the potential to serve as an absolute breeding spot for both pathogenic and nonpathogenic organism. This concurs with the work of Furedy [10], who stated that open dumps have environmental safeguards; they can pose major public health threats and environmental effects in urban cities. In addition, dumpsites closer to residential areas are always feeding places for dogs and cats. These pets, together with rodents, carry diseases with them to nearby homesteads. Results from the analysis of data revealed that both nearby residents and far away residents suffered from related diseases due to the location of the dumpsite closer to their settlements. It was discovered that residents less than fifty meters from the dumpsite are most affected by the dumpsite. It was also noted that the extent of air and water pollution is worse in the raining season as a result of offensive odour, as well as ground water pollution. In the dry season, the smoke from the incineration of

the dumpsite is an important source of air pollution for people living far away from the dumpsite. The study therefore concludes that the dumpsite should be properly situated and carefully managed to minimize its negative effects on the environment and improved health the status of the populace living less than fifty meters away from the dumpsite. The populace needs to be health educated by health motivators about the effects of waste dumping and defecating at such dumpsites which could expose them to many hazards.

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